

Effect of Tumour Development on Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase of Host's Liver

M. M. DOHADWALA, A. G. DATTA & L. CHAUDHURI*

Indian Institute of Experimental Medicine, Calcutta.

Manuscript received 29 July 1977, revised 10 August 1977 : accepted 12 August 1977

Liver glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase activity of Ehrlich ascites carcinoma bearing mice and of mice with skin carcinoma was found to be increased with the development of the tumour. Administration of mitomycin C and rifampicin reveals a definite tumour-host relationship as regards the liver glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase activity.

GLUCOSE-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G-6-PD) activity was reported to be increased in hepatomas and other tumours¹⁻⁵. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to study the behaviour of this enzyme in liver during carcinogenesis in mice bearing fast-growing Ehrlich ascites tumour and slow growing methyl cholanthrene induced carcinoma. The present paper provides information as to this assessment and liver G-6-PD activity has been found to be proportional to the growth of these two types of tumours.

Experimental

Ehrlich ascites carcinoma (EAC) was maintained in Swiss male mice weighing 15-20 gms by interperitoneal inoculation of 0.2 ml of ascitic fluid. Iliac region of Swiss male mice of 18-20 gms in average weight were shaved 24 hrs before the first painting and a single brush stroke of 20-Methylcholanthrene (0.5% solution in benzene) was applied to that area thrice in a week, over a period of 14 weeks. Another set of mice with benzene painting was kept as control.

Liver was homogenized in 0.25 M sucrose solution. Supernatant fraction, after centrifugation at 105,000 g for hr was used for assay. The enzyme was assayed spectrophotometrically⁶ by following increase of optical density at 340 nm. Specific activity was expressed as μ moles of TPN⁺ reduced/mg protein/min. Protein was determined by the method of Lowry *et al*⁷.

Mitomycin C (4 mg/kg b.w.) and Rifampicin (100 μ g/kg b.w.) were injected interperitoneally in EAC-bearing mice. The serial injection (one injection per day) was started 30 mins after transplantation of the tumour and was continued till 10th day. The animals were sacrificed 24 hrs after each injection. Peritoneal fluid of the transplanted animal was taken out in a centrifuge tube. The cells were washed repeatedly with 0.85% saline and the packed cell volume (ml) was determined after centrifugation at 3000 g for 10 minutes.

Results

It can be seen from Fig 1, that the G-6-PD activity in liver increases significantly with the development of the tumour. Within 4th day after transplantation, when the tumour was not even perceptible, the enzyme activity increased by about 40% above the enzyme activity of the normal liver. The increase was very rapid between 2nd and 4th day and was about 79% on 10th day.

Fig 1. Liver G-6-PD activity of Ehrlich ascites carcinoma-bearing mice.

(○—○) normal liver ;
(●—●) liver of EAC-bearing mice.

In case of slow-growing induced carcinoma, liver G-6-PD showed 27% increase in activity over that of the control liver after one month (Table 1). Incidentally, papilloma was not found at all during this period. Consequently, with the development of carcinoma, activity increased to about 60% on 3rd month. The results showed that during the course of epidermal carcinogenesis, the enzyme activity in

liver increased and reached a higher level than that found in the liver of benzene-painted mice.

TABLE 1.

Liver G-6-PD activity in 20-methylcholanthrene treated mice.

Days of treatment	Weight of the liver (mg)	Sp. Activity (μ moles of TPN ⁺ reduced/mg protein/minutes)
<i>Liver of Benzene painted mice.</i>		
30	800	0.04
60	900	0.044
90	900	0.052
<i>Liver of 20-methylcholanthrene painted mice</i>		
30	800	0.051
60	700	0.076
90	600	0.083

Values are an average of three experiments.

Hence, some antitumour agents were used to study their effect on tumour growth as well as on the enzyme activity. It can be observed from Table 2 that the administration of mitomycin-C to the transplanted mice caused a regression of ascites tumour without any change in enzyme activity in liver. With rifampicin, however, the liver enzyme activity increased progressively along with the growth of the tumour.

TABLE 2

Effects of Mitomycin C and Rifampicin on EAC-bearing mice.

	Days after transplantation.	Packed cell vol. (ml)	Specific activity of liver G-6-PD (μ moles of TPN ⁺ reduced/mg protein/min).
<i>Mitomycin C</i>	1	0.2	0.06
	3	0.2	0.061
	5	0.1	0.064
	7	0.02	0.064
	9	Nil	0.06
	11	Nil	0.06
<i>Rifampicin</i>	1	0.1	0.06
	3	0.3	0.072
	5	0.1	0.08
	7	0.5	0.088
	9	1.0	0.09
	11	1.3	0.13

Each value represents the average of three experiments.

Discussion

We selected fast-growing Ehrlich ascites tumour and slow-growing methylcholanthrene-induced carcinoma for our study because the definite change in enzyme activity in both cases will show how tumour growth affects the enzyme activity of the host's liver. The data obtained under these two conditions, show a definite increase in G-6-PD activity in host's liver when tumours were still very small. The increased level of activity was very significant when the tumour attains its maximum size. The packed cell volume can be taken as a measure of the growth of Ehrlich ascites tumour. The increase in enzyme activity in liver of benzene-painted animal may be due to some toxic effect. But this increase in activity is much less in comparison to that of the methylcholanthrene painted mice.

Experiments with rifampicin and mitomycin-C show the effect of tumour growth on the level of enzyme activity in liver. The reason for rifampicin not having any inhibitory effect on the growth of tumour could be due to the fact that rifampicin is not very much effective in eukaryotic cells. It can thus be concluded that the tumour development has definite correlation with liver G-6-PD activity, which is quite significant from the early stage of malignancy.

Acknowledgements

One of us (M.M.D) is grateful to C.S.I.R. for the award of a junior research fellowship.

References

1. S. KIT ; *Cancer Res.*, 1956, **16**, 70.
2. C. WU and H. A. HOMBURGER ; *Brit. J. Cancer*, 1969, **23**, 204.
3. F. B. HERSHEY, G. JHONSTON, S. M. MURPHY and M. SCHMITT ; *Cancer Res.*, 1966, **26**, 256.
4. S. GUENTER ; *Arch. Geschwulstforsch.*, 1970, **35** (4), 379.
5. B. L. RUBENCHICK , *Vop. Eksp. Onkol.*, 1969 (4), 20.
6. A. KORNBERG and B. L. HOREKER ; *Methods in Enzymology*, 1955, **1**, 323.
7. O. H. LOWRY, N. J. ROSEBROUGH, A. L. FAR and R. J. RANDALL ; *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1951, **193**, 265.